

Thiazolinylhydrazones. Part II*. Synthesis of 4-Oxo-5-alkyl/aryl- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones

P. R. Pathan, B. K. Raval, and J. J. Trivedi

4-Oxo-5-alkyl/aryl- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones have been prepared by condensing aryl thiosemicarbazones with appropriate α -bromo- acids.

In the present investigation aryl thiosemicarbazones have been condensed with α -bromovaleric^a, α -bromocaproic^a, α -bromo-*p*-chlorophenyl, α -*p*-dibromophenyl- and α -bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl-acetic acids to yield the corresponding 4-oxo-5-alkyl/aryl- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiosemicarbazones were prepared from the aromatic aldehydes and thiosemicarbazide by the procedure of Buu-Hoi^b *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 415; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 715).

α -Bromo-fatty acids were prepared by bromination of valeric^a and caproic^a acids (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1951, p. 421).

α -Bromo-arylacetic acids were prepared, as described by Raval and Trivedi (this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 733) from the corresponding mandelic acids, which in turn were prepared from the corresponding aldehydes.

Thiosemicarbazones were condensed with the α -bromo-acids as described by Buu-Hoi^b *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Thiazolinylhydrazones were obtained in 40-80% yields and were crystallised from acetic acid. Compounds are listed in Table I.

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TABLE I

4-Oxo-5-alkyl/aryl- Δ^3 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones.

X	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
H	204°	$C_{11}H_{15}ON_2S$	12.1	12.3	204°	$R' = \text{Butyl}^a$	11.7	11.6	258°	$R' = p\text{-ClPh.}$	9.8	9.7
<i>o</i> -Cl	176°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2ClS$	10.6	10.8	180°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2S$	10.1	10.3	262°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2ClS$	8.6	8.8
<i>p</i> -Cl	200°	"	11.0	"	200°	"	10.5	"	252°	"	8.9	8.8
<i>o</i> -Me	178°	$C_{12}H_{17}ON_2S$	11.5	11.6	171°	$C_{12}H_{17}ON_2S$	11.3	11.1	260°	$C_{12}H_{17}ON_2ClS$	9.1	9.3
<i>o</i> -OH	224°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_2N_2S$	11.7	11.6	224°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_2N_2S$	10.9	11.0	260°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_2N_2ClS$	9.5	9.3
<i>p</i> -OH	278°	"	11.5	"	278°	"	11.2	"	"	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -OMe	163°	$C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_2S$	11.1	11.0	166°	$C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_2S$	10.7	10.5	159°	$C_{17}H_{25}O_4N_2ClS$	9.0	8.9
<i>p</i> -OMe	178°	"	10.9	"	169°	"	10.6	"	248°	$C_{17}H_{25}O_4N_2ClS$	8.8	8.9
2,4-Di-Cl	176°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	9.9	9.7	200°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	9.4	9.3	274°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	8.1	8.0
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	235°	$C_{12}H_{19}ON_4S$	10.6	10.5	224°	$C_{12}H_{19}ON_2S$	10.0	10.1	280°	$C_{12}H_{17}ON_2ClS$	8.8	8.6
5-Cl-2-OH	234°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_2N_2ClS$	10.5	10.3	230°	$C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_2ClS$	10.0	9.8	248°	$C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_2Cl_2S$	8.6	8.4
H	262°	$C_{10}H_{13}ON_2BrS$	8.8	8.6		$R' = p\text{-Br-Ph.}$						
<i>o</i> -Cl	268°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2BrS$	8.0	7.8		X.						
<i>o</i> -Me	264°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2ClBrS$	8.5	8.3		<i>p</i> -Cl			274°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	8.5	8.3
<i>o</i> -OH	254°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_2N_2BrS$	8.0	8.2		<i>o</i> -Me			297°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	8.4	8.5
<i>o</i> -OMe	264°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_2N_2BrS$	7.7	7.9		<i>p</i> -OH			308°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_2S$	8.2	8.4
<i>p</i> -OMe	248°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_2N_2BrS$	8.0	7.9		<i>o</i> -OMe			286°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_2S$	8.3	8.1
2,4-Di-Cl	260°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2BrS$	7.1	7.2		<i>p</i> -OMe			262°	"	8.0	8.1
						2, 4-Di-Cl			294°	$C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl_2S$	7.6	7.4

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. C. SCIENCE INSTITUTE,
AHMEDABAD-9.

AND
L. H. SCIENCE & S. D. ARTS COLLEGE,
MANSI (N. GUJARAT).

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